

**PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS
OF SOCIAL-INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY OF YOUTH**

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It can be observed that the number of young people is growing rapidly worldwide. According to the data, "the population of the world is more than 7.6 billion, 31.5% of them are young people under 30 years old". The growth rate of the youth population has a great impact on the political, economic and social spheres of the country. This, in turn, depends on the attention of the state to young people, the conditions created for young people to build their lives, the extent to which their rights and interests are protected, and the privileges given to realize their potential through their talents and abilities. Therefore, the issue of improving the social mobility of young people and harmonizing it with the times is of urgent importance.

In the research conducted on youth social mobility in the world, including the statistical dynamics of unemployment, various forms of migration, and employment issues directly related to youth social mobility (International Association of Survey Statisticians (IASS), Netherlands), youth social mobility arising in the conditions of transformation and modernization (European Survey Research Association, UK), educational opportunities of young people in the process of social stratification, educational migration and proper organization of free time of young people (World Association for Public Opinion Research (WAPOR), USA) promotes the need to improve the system.

In our country, special attention is paid to the creation of modern conditions and opportunities for the education and occupation of young people in various spheres of society's life, and at the same time, to organize meaningful leisure time

for them. "It is necessary to develop uniform indicators for evaluating the effectiveness of working with youth, to introduce a national index of youth policy evaluation. It is necessary that the Youth Union of Uzbekistan should develop the concept "Youth of Uzbekistan - 2025", in which practical measures to raise a mentally and physically mature generation should be determined. Stages and processes of socialization of young people, addressing problems related to social mobility in their social stratification processes, systematic regulation of organizational processes of social mobility and social movements of young people and social groups, and further improvement of the complex socio-sociological system that helps to create the necessary opportunities in this regard. implementation is of significant scientific and practical importance.

1. In the view of the modern world, people living in society are always on the move, and society is always developing. This situation means the constant change of the social structure of the society.

2. In the history of mankind, not only the change of the position of an individual in social life, but also the change of the social position of entire social groups is observed. This includes the arrival of the financial bourgeoisie instead of the aristocracy of large landowners, small producers with a narrow range of knowledge and skills, i.e. instead of crafts, engineers, programmers (programmers), production controlled by robotics, operators, to be more precise, the arrival of advanced innovative scientific techniques or XIX- We know from history that as a result of the wars and revolutions that occurred in the 20th century, the economy of some countries developed, while others faced a crisis. We are witnessing such changes in Uzbekistan. A clear example of this is the arrival of the elite of owners, entrepreneurs and businessmen who are owners of large property after independence.

3. As a result of the independence of Uzbekistan and the construction of a new state and a new society in the country, the problems of social mobility became particularly relevant during the modernization of the society of Uzbekistan. Under

the conditions of independence, favorable conditions for the rapid implementation of the concept of social mobility have arisen in Uzbekistan.

4. The actions and political struggles for the country's independence and strengthening of its independence have ended, and now humanity has entered the stage of high intellectual development. This stage of social development is new, the construction of society based on its own laws has become a reality. As Abu Rayhan Beruni noted, "In fact, science arises from the need to satisfy people's vital needs. After knowing the true history of the people, they began to realize their identity."

5. Today, the scientists of our country are conducting effective work on the analysis of socio-professional and economic mobility, including its subjective aspect, considering the trends of social mobility of various strata and groups of modern Uzbekistan society, and developing methods of empirical measurement of various forms of social mobility in modern conditions.

6. In the life of the population of our country, the most intensive social mobility occurs partially from the age of 14 and completely from the age of 16 to 30. Factors that make young people a socio-demographic group with high levels of social mobility include:

7. 1. Transition from education to work, integration of the individual into the socio-professional structure of the society, gaining an independent economic status. A number of researchers consider the time of transition to work as the lowest age limit of young people. "Youth," says M. Rutkevich, "generally means a socio-demographic group whose members are physically and mentally mature, unlike children and teenagers, and are ready to actively and independently participate in society's life, first of all, in production." F. Filippov put forward a similar opinion, and in his opinion, the social nature of young people is largely determined by work.

8. Usually, by the age of 30, as a result of a person's personal achievements, the ground is laid for his future service career, and he realizes increasing vertical

mobility.

9. The start of work of young people makes it possible to compare the social achievements of parents for people from different backgrounds, to determine the level of influence of social background on future professional and other success, and other aspects of intergenerational social mobility.

10. Until the age of 30, young people build their families and give birth to their children.

In this way, compared to other groups, it is the young people who occupy the main place in the growing social mobility, activity and social mobility. All this makes it possible to describe young people as the most dynamic group and explains the relevance of researching the mechanisms of regulation of social mobility of this socio-demographic group.

The concept of "youth social mobility" in a broad sense, social mobility is the social dynamics of young people, that is, the social movement of young people and their separate groups under the influence of various factors. The fact that the structure of society includes many social positions explains the diversity of social mobility processes.

Based on the direction of actions, the spheres of social life in which they occur, the number of participants and other criteria, youth social mobility is divided into transition to higher layers, classes, strata (increasing mobility) and transition to lower layers, classes, strata (decreasing mobility).

In social reality, only vertical movement is not widespread, and in many respects the ideal type, which is explained by the withdrawal from science in the study of these processes. Classification of socio-economic positions of individuals, families, social groups (according to the level of income) is not complicated. It is also easy to stratify the population in terms of education. But if we try to put these two dimensions into one system, it becomes clear that high income is not always the reason for high level of education, in many cases it is the opposite, that is,

investments determine the size and quality of education.

Political and professional stratification does not give the same result. Horizontal mobility is the movement of individuals and social groups from one social position to another, but to a position of the same level (of equal status). At the same time, it should be noted that objectively equal social positions may be subjectively more useful or unprofitable under the influence of additional factors. Therefore, the transition from one religious denomination to another, from one state citizenship to another, from one marriage to another, from one profession to another, etc., are not considered purely horizontal movements, because in many cases they also lead to a change in economic, political, and interpersonal status.

Financial actions that change the status of a young person constitute the essence of economic mobility. In modern conditions, this is also confirmed by the results of various sociological studies, the economic status of an individual is determined by the most important indicators such as his income, the form of ownership of the enterprise he works for, and his attitude to property.

The following factors serve as the factors of the growing social mobility of young people: political and economic stability, wide range of mobility in society, high level of education of parents, material well-being, being in the city, being employed in commercial or private entrepreneurship, having certain personal qualities (diligence, aspiration, communication, flexibility, readiness for changes). Factors of decreasing mobility are sudden changes in the social structure of society, political and economic recessions, inadequacy of training of specialists in certain professions to the needs of the labor market, lack of higher education in parents, below average level of material security, living in rural areas, employment in the budget sector, low starting salary of young employees, laziness, lack of initiative, lack of ambition, etc.

Political mobility refers to changes in individuals or social groups. The political position is explained by the powers of authority that this or that person

has. At the moment, not only officials in the state administration system, but also leaders of political parties, managers of military and law enforcement agencies, large corporations, media leaders, etc. have high political positions.

Increasing powers of authority is an integral aspect of moving up the service ladder, one of the indicators of professional mobility. Therefore, models of political stratification and political mobility are explained with great uncertainty.

Actions affecting the change of professional positions of individuals or social groups are manifested in professional mobility. One of the types of youth professional mobility is job change. This mobility may be associated with a change in job or specialty, or with the persistence of these symptoms. One of the important indicators of professional mobility is the service career - the transition from an executive job to a managerial job. Professional mobility is explained by an increase in the individual's qualifications, the improvement of professional skills, thereby gaining a higher rank, title, academic degree, etc.

One of the most important aspects characteristic of an individual in modern societies is the level of education, and its change is educational mobility. The educational status of a person in Uzbekistan is explained by the existence of basic, general secondary, secondary special vocational, higher education and post-university education levels. An additional factor affecting education and professional mobility is training and retraining courses. As one of the directions of educational mobility of young people, moving from one educational institution to another based on the prestige of the educational place, such actions can increase or decrease the educational status of a person.

The change in the social status of young people in various spheres of society's life compared to the status of their parents constitutes intergenerational mobility. Intergenerational mobility is an important factor of social change and a manifestation of social activity of individuals. The change in the social status of children compared to the social status of their parents is one of the indicators of a

rapidly developing society.

Based on the number of participants, social mobility is divided into individual mobility (movements of individuals) and collective mobility (changes in the status of social groups, classes). Various factors influence the mobility of individuals and groups.

First, the system of stratification, which is manifested in the importance attached to a predetermined and achieved position. When societal institutions focus heavily on established status, collective or group mobility tendencies emerge. Individual mobility tends to prevail in societies with a strong emphasis on achieved status.

Second, social background (race, nationality, age, etc.) appears as an obstacle to individual mobility. For this reason, some social strata strive for collective mobility so that the predetermined status of group members does not hinder their success. Examples of this are various movements, including those fighting to restore and preserve the rights of national and racial minorities, those fighting to give more rights to women, etc. The success of these actions indicates that a previously established position can be changed as a result of collective efforts.

Thirdly, various social instability (revolution, war, military rebellion, coup d'etats, rallies, demonstrations, etc.) affects the change in the status of social groups.

Depending on the level of influence of the state on social movements, social mobility will be chaotic and organized. Organized mobility is carried out in two ways:

- a) with the consent of the people;
- b) without their consent.

In a narrow sense, the concept of "youth social mobility" is used in two

senses. First, it is a social movement that changes the social position of the subject, first of all a young person. Secondly, this concept refers to one of the stages of the process of social dynamics of young people, that is, the ability to act.

Therefore, it depends on the youth to act on their own and the state and society to create sufficient conditions for the social movement of the youth. It also depends on the capital invested by the parents in their children for social activities and the ability of the children to assimilate this invested capital.

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